

Supplemental Figure S1. Quantification of RYK-V5 immunoblots. (A-B) Quantification of RYK-V5 CTF (A) and RYK-V5 ICD (B) shown in main text Figure 3A. (C-D) Quantification of RYK-V5 CTF (C) and RYK-V5 ICD (D) shown in Figure 3B. (E-F) Quantification of RYK-V5 FL (E) and RYK-V5 CTF (F) shown in Figure 6B.